

Demystifying Gender and Development (GAD): A Review of Impact and Challenges

Cynic Tenedero

Technological University of the Philippines,
Philippines
cynicjazmintenedero@gmail.com

Marie Jo Tess Ragos

Technological University of the Philippines,
Philippines

Muajiz Muallim

Institut Agama Islam Negeri Parepare,
Indonesia

Received:12/11/2025 Accepted:12/11/2025 Published:12/31/2025

Abstract

Gender and Development (GAD) serves as a critical framework in addressing gender disparities by integrating gender analysis into development policies and programs, despite global efforts to promote gender equality, challenges persist in social, economic, and political spheres. A descriptive library - research design was utilized to analyze challenges and impact in Gender and Development Component through Conceptual Analysis by Furner (2004). Studies show that gendered social norms can hinder the benefits of gender-neutral programs for girls in low- and middle-income countries. However, some programs, like female role models and group learning, can provide more benefits for girls. Further research is needed to understand the varying effects of these programs. The challenges nested in gender inequality, gender and development are assured using applicable gender analysis-based policies. The significance of gender-responsive education is increasing as a strategy to eradicate gender-based disparities within the educational system and to acknowledge the unique learning requirements of each student. While significant efforts have been made through policy frameworks, institutional mechanisms, and targeted interventions, achieving true gender equality remains an ongoing process requiring continuous evaluation and adaptation. To address these challenges, a multifaceted approach is required, involving stricter policy enforcement, educational reforms, and greater advocacy for gender-inclusive policies. Future research should focus on intersectional gender disparities, LGBTQ+ inclusion, and the impact of digital economies on gender relations. By prioritizing gender equality and mainstreaming, societies can move toward sustainable development where all individuals, regardless of gender, have equal opportunities to thrive.

Keywords: Gender and Development (GAD), gender equality, impact, challenges

Introduction

Gender and Development (GAD) is a framework aimed at addressing gender inequality by integrating gender analysis into development policies and programs (Ridgeway and Correll, 2004). It aims to promote equal rights and opportunities for all genders, acknowledging the socially constructed nature of gender roles and their influence on economic and social systems (Reeves and Baden, 2000). Despite global efforts, significant challenges persist in achieving gender equality. The United Nations launched the Decade for Women (1976-1985), which marked a turning point in recognizing women's rights on a global scale. Over forty years, international donors and governments have prioritized gender inclusivity policies. However, significant gaps remain, particularly in women's economic participation and ownership rights. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have reinforced the commitment to integrating gender considerations into policy implementations (Grown et al., 2016).

Gender stereotypes and institutional biases continue to delay policy enforcement (UNDP, 2020). Despite legal provisions, gender inequality remains elusive due to long-established societal norms and cultural constraints (UN Women, 2022). Gender-based disparities in labor force participation and wages remain prevalent. Women continue to earn less than men, with limited access to high-paying job opportunities. The unadjusted gender pay gap reflects broad economic inequalities. In contrast, the adjusted pay gap accounts for education and work experience, but even with these factors considered, women still earn less than men in various fields (Ortiz-Ospina et al., 2018). Women often balance professional responsibilities and unpaid domestic labor, which limits their opportunities for career growth. Despite legal frameworks supporting workplace equality, societal expectations continue to limit women's career advancement (Đundić, 2024). Women in rural communities' struggle with gender-biased land ownership policies, limiting their economic independence (Bejeno, 2021). While legal reforms have improved access to land titles, implementation remains inconsistent, particularly in indigenous and rural areas (Dealca, 2025).

Gender perception influences online victimization and aggression. Masculine-typed traits have been linked to cyberbullying, while individuals who are content with their gender identity are less likely to be victims of cyberbullying (Navarro, 2015). Studies indicate that males externalize behaviors such as aggression more, while females tend to internalize emotions, leading to higher rates of anxiety and depression (Ara, 2015). Despite ongoing debates on gender similarities, statistical methods confirm distinct patterns in gender-based social behavior (Del Guidice, 2015). Gender mainstreaming ensures the integration of gender equality across all levels of decision-making (Eagly and Carli, 2007). Laws such as the Magna Carta of Women have advanced gender equality, but enforcement remains inconsistent (WEF, 2024). Although economic growth is linked to greater gender equality, cultural and legal barriers continue to hinder full equality. Progressive policies often struggle against traditional gender norms that reinforce systemic inequalities (Jayachandran, 2015)

Despite significant progress, research gaps remain in areas such as LGBTQ+ inclusion in gender policies, intersectionality in gender studies where LGBTQ+ experiences are often

overlooked and the impact of digital economies on gender discrimination. Further investigation into the long-term effectiveness of gender policies is needed to address these challenges comprehensively.

The pursuit of gender equality remains a significant challenge despite global efforts and policy advancements. While legal frameworks and gender advocacy efforts have contributed to progress, unwavering social, economic, and political barriers continue to hinder full equality. The gender wage gap, unequal labor divisions, and limited land ownership opportunities for women demonstrate the ongoing struggles to achieve gender equality. Additionally, deeply ingrained cultural norms and biases delay the implementation of progressive policies. Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive approach, including stricter enforcement of existing laws, expanding education initiatives, and continued advocacy for marginalized groups.

Methods

This article reviews the challenges and impact of Gender and Development Component. This is a descriptive library - research design, which required the writer to collect the object materials from the previous studies related to Gender. Jones (1993) advocated that this type of research design would assist the researcher in attaching and identifying the factual sources or personal ideas to answer related research objective.

The sources in this research include published papers on the impact and challenges of gender and development components by integrating gender analysis into development policies and programs. Furthermore, the focus of the writers in this paper is on the challenges and differences in the components of gender and development.

The research utilized descriptive research anchored by a library research design. The data was analyzed through Conceptual Analysis by Furner (2004) of the published papers regarding Gender and Development Components. The analysis of Furner (2004) allowed the researcher to evaluate the concept of evidence to improve understanding of archival concepts. The researcher's analysis involves identifying the gender and development components in terms of challenges and impact, and the research selection extracts keywords and content. The data gathered and analyzed through summarizing, synthesizing, or comparing different sources. Lastly, the evaluation of sources involves identifying the research credibility, publication date, and the relevance of the paper.

Figure 1. A review of the structure of Gender and Development Components

Figure 1 presents the connection between the impact and challenges in the components of Gender and Development. This includes gender analysis, gender - responsive education and gender audit.

Results and Discussion

Gender Analysis

In the social, political, and economic spheres of society, both men and women are important. Battad (2006) asserts that gender equality is a fundamental human right. Women play a significant role in the workplace that cannot be disregarded. While the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2022) reports a global Gender Inequality Index (GII) of 0.462, the Philippines, on the other hand, possesses a GII of 0.388. These scores highlight gender-based inequality in health, empowerment, and labor market participation, echoing the disadvantages of socioeconomic development. In general, women continue to receive, on average, 23% less than men across the globe in the labor market, and they do approximately three times more unpaid care and household work than men (Dula, 2019). This persistent disparity illustrates a structural contradiction within GAD implementation, where gender equality is formally recognized in policy but undermined by entrenched socio-cultural expectations that normalize women's unpaid labor. As a result, economic empowerment initiatives often fail to translate into substantive equality. Although women's voice, mobility, and role in conflict resolution have grown, the field still faces many obstacles to their meaningful involvement in peace building and socioeconomic development because these depend on social class, religion, ethnicity, and social status (Reyes et al., 2017). However, following a catastrophe, this disruption in social norms usually goes away, and regular gender standards typically return when communities are rebuilding and resettling (Herrero, 2019). Women and the most vulnerable groups, Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program/ (4Ps), solo parents, experience compounded burdens (Dizon and Medina, 2020). The stark contrast between the societal construction of gender norms and what it means to be a woman and a man, and the actual actions is astounding (Libre, 2017).

Aside from households, the labor sector also shows the disparities between men and women. The report released by the International Labor Organization (ILO, 2022) highlights the labor force participation rate for both genders, with a global labor rate of 47% for women and 72% for men. As a result, it is more difficult for women to find employment than for men. In the Philippines, women comprise 43.8% of the labor force population, while 68.3% remain for men. (PSA, 2016). It also shows that men have higher average wages compared to women, added by the fact that the latter tend to be in vulnerable or informal work. Reducing gender gaps in labor force participation is important as it could substantially boost the global GDP (ILO, 2022).

While some gender-related factors are being shed light upon, politics for women is also crucial in the Philippines. Since women make up half of the population and ought to be

fairly represented in political processes, their involvement in electoral politics is essential to bolstering democracy (Encinas-Franco & Laguna, 2023). Only 19 percent of all barangay captain and councilperson positions were held by women at the barangay level (Philippine Institute for Development Studies, 2021). Focusing on women's issues rather than masculinity is another important factor that influences the political calculations and choices made by men in politics who advocate for gender equality. Their work on gender equality mostly focuses on women, with little attention paid to masculinity (Michalko et al., 2024).

The education sector presents no inequality for men and women when it comes to admission, with 99.9% reported parity (Philippine Institute for Development Studies, 2023). Still, cultural norms, gender biases, and limited mentorship opportunities continue to be a hurdle when it comes to pursuing STEM fields (Sison, 2023). Nonetheless, gender-gap reversal is tending to happen, with more Filipino boys lagging earlier in their path. The lower academic performance of boys relative to girls in elementary and secondary education is contributing to the tending disparity of women to men student ratio in college (Paqueo et al., 2019). Such an inequality stresses that empowerment should not come at the expense of other genders.

Despite the challenges nested in gender inequality, gender and development are assured using applicable gender analysis-based policies. Such is gender mainstreaming, which guarantees that the government puts a priority on gender equality in all socioeconomic sectors (Philippine Commission on Women, 2019). This process imposes the transformation of social, political, and economic spheres of society.

Gender – Responsive Education

Education is considered a critical instrument for achieving gender equality and accelerating the progress of a nation (Khaiwal and Gupta, 2023). Gender-responsive education promotes inclusivity by addressing gender biases in academic, technical, and professional training. However, evidence suggests that such interventions are effective only when accompanied by teacher capacity-building and institutional commitment. Without these supporting mechanisms, gender-responsive policies risk becoming symbolic rather than transformative, reproducing existing inequalities within classroom practices. By implementing gender-sensitive policies, schools and workplaces create equal opportunities for students and employees to develop essential skills for career advancement (Llego, 2019b).

(Abraha et al, 2019) highlighted that education as the most effective tool for promoting gender - equality and ensuring equitable growth. Despite this, it is observed that teachers and students are sometimes unable to comprehend the varying needs of boys and girls based on gender. Therefore, it is imperative to address this issue and promote equal opportunities for all. An educational institution is crucial in shaping individuals' thoughts and instilling societal norms and expected behaviors. Additionally, it influences how people perceive themselves (Lorber, 2008; Bowles & Gintis, 2009). Consequently, the school's teaching-learning process plays a significant role in shaping gender identity. If there is an imbalance in how this identity is defined and developed, it will lead to gender bias. Additionally, this mindset will foster expectations and reinforce gender stereotypes. It will perpetuate differentiated functions and

training for males and females from the early stages of life to adulthood (Weis and Fine, 2005). Numerous studies demonstrate gender prejudice and preconceptions present in classroom instruction. Without addressing gender issues both within and outside of the classroom, quality education cannot be delivered. Although teachers use teaching methods or strategies in the classroom, they do not provide boys and girls with equal opportunities to engage in the teaching and learning process (Mlama et al., 2005).

The Ministry of Education, alongside schools, should implement capacity building for teachers and education officials to help them acquire gender-responsive skills in their daily teaching and learning activities, as well as to foster a positive attitude towards gender equity using a bottom-up approach (Dorji, 2020). Educational institutions can employ gender-sensitive teaching strategies within and outside the classroom to promote equality and foster a favorable learning climate for everyone (Khalil et al., 2024). The tutors sampled in the key courses (English, Math, and Science) have positively changed and embraced the use of gender-responsive pedagogy. Both male and female instructors are increasingly utilizing gender-sensitive teaching methods. Additionally, the application of gender-responsive mentoring strategies by mentors has also seen improvement (Ananga et al., 2021). By utilizing a gender-responsive pedagogy approach, educators can provide equal assistance to both male and female students while tackling gender bias in the teaching and learning processes within a predominantly male educational setting. Education is considered a tool to attain global equality between men and women (Kahamba et al., 2017).

The significance of gender-responsive education is increasing as a strategy to eradicate gender-based disparities within the educational system and to acknowledge the unique learning requirements of each student. An important part of the process is played by those who train instructors (tutors), who serve as a link between academic concepts and students' actual classroom experiences (Rarieya et al., 2024). The goal is to broaden students' perspectives on social issues to effectively analyze the challenges facing Philippine society. By making the curriculum gender-responsive, we can encourage students to gather insights and practices from their social environments, allowing both boys and girls to gain a comprehensive understanding of their roles as female and male. A gender-fair curriculum will help students learn how to respect and commit themselves to improving the needs and welfare of both males and females, watch for biases, share information, and build a network of colleagues with a strong commitment to gender equity (Tantengco, 2013). Unless a focus is made on the system of education itself, not only the number of girls compared to the number of boys in school but also what is taught and how it is taught (Aikman et al., 2005).

Gender Audit

Gender equality and mainstreaming have become central themes in both local and international discourse, reflecting a global commitment to addressing disparities and promoting inclusivity. While the significance of gender equality is widely acknowledged, its complexities and the factors contributing to persistent inequalities remain less understood by many (Armar, 2024). This review of related literature examines various studies and frameworks, both within the Philippines and globally, that shed light on the challenges and strategies involved in achieving gender equality across different sectors. These studies explore issues ranging from subtle biases and institutional barriers to active policy implementation

and evaluation mechanisms, highlighting the ongoing efforts and the distance yet to be covered in realizing true gender parity.

Locally, research in the Philippines reveals a diverse landscape of gender-related issues and initiatives. Studies in Marikina's public schools, the City of Mati, CALABARZON's law enforcement, the University of Bohol, and barangay governance in Mati have identified specific challenges such as bullying, inadequate facilities, early stages of gender mainstreaming, and obstacles to women's involvement in decision-making (Abulencia et al., 2023; Hemillan et al., 2021; Pulongon & Tirol, 2013; Quilapio et al., 2024). These findings underscore the necessity for tailored interventions, policy enhancements, and capacity-building programs to address context-specific gender inequalities.

Furthermore, the Philippine government has established frameworks such as the Gender Mainstreaming Evaluation Framework (GMEF) and the Gender and Development Focal Point System (GFPS) to assess and monitor progress in gender mainstreaming (Philippine Commission on Women, 2022). Policies like CHED Memorandum Order No. 01 (2015) also aim to institutionalize gender equality in higher education. Gender audits are recognized as crucial tools for identifying weaknesses in gender equality programs and informing targeted interventions (Villegas et al., 2023).

While gender audits are designed to evaluate institutional commitment to gender equality, their effectiveness often depends on political will and organizational culture. In many cases, audits function primarily as compliance mechanisms rather than as tools for structural transformation. This creates a contradiction within the GAD framework, institutions may demonstrate formal adherence to gender mainstreaming requirements while substantive gender inequalities persist in everyday practices. Consequently, gender audits risk reinforcing procedural accountability without addressing deeper power relations that sustain inequality.

Internationally, gender mainstreaming is recognized as the primary strategy for achieving gender equality, with governments integrating gender considerations into various development sectors (UN Women-Headquarters, 2022). Research on joint audit environments suggests that gender-diverse audit partners can enhance decision-making and reduce earnings management (Nekhili et al., 2022). Studies also indicate the influence of female board directors on the gender assignment of audit partners, highlighting the importance of gender in corporate governance (Hossain & Chapple, 2022). Moreover, participatory gender audits are advocated by organizations like the OSCE Parliamentary Assembly (2020) and Akina Mama wa Afrika (2020) as vital processes for evaluating gender mainstreaming within institutions, identifying areas for improvement, and fostering a culture of accountability.

In conclusion, the body of literature reviewed emphasizes the persistent and multifaceted nature of gender disparity, both locally and globally. While significant efforts have been made through policy frameworks, institutional mechanisms, and targeted interventions, achieving true gender equality remains an ongoing process requiring continuous evaluation and adaptation. The importance of addressing gender issues lies in its fundamental impact on human rights, social justice, and sustainable development. By

understanding the complexities and implementing evidence-based strategies, societies can move towards more inclusive and equitable futures where all individuals, regardless of gender, have equal opportunities and are empowered to reach their full potential.

The Academic Challenges in Gender

The gender role in academic performance is still an issue that attracts increased scientific interest, mainly due to the inconclusive reported findings. Several studies suggest that females outperform males in language-based subjects and verbal tests (Deary et al., 2006; Spinath et al., 2009), and males outperform their female counterparts in STEM-related subjects (math, engineering, etc.) and visuospatial tests (Strand et al., 2006; Lakin, 2013).

According to Downey and Vogt Yuan (2005), certain traits and practices linked to or contrasted with masculinity or femininity can have a positive or negative impact on the academic performance of both sexes. For instance, some studies have found that masculine stereotypes portray boys as dominant, competitive, and active, whilst girls are portrayed as conciliatory (Francis, 2002; Legewie & DiPrete, 2009). Gender is one of such factors to have considerable effects on students' academic performance, especially in science subjects; it relates to the range of physical, biological, mental, and behavioral characteristics about and differentiating between feminine and masculine (male and female) populations.

Academic performance, learning preferences, and subject choices are all greatly influenced by gender. Gender has a big impact on subject choices, learning styles, and academic achievement. Boys tend to do better in science and math, while girls tend to do better in language arts and reading, according to research. Rather than natural abilities, social norms often influence these findings. Gender identity is impacted by a combination of biological traits, developmental aspects, and environmental factors, in addition to biological sex. Educators must understand this idea to establish a welcoming atmosphere that values and fosters each child's gender diversity. Researchers analyzed the academic performance of ninth-grade students in Nepal, demonstrating that female students consistently surpassed their male peers (Parajuli and Thapa (2017). Their studies also revealed that private school students exceeded public school pupils in terms of task completion, attendance, and assertiveness. Similarly, it explored gender inequalities in academic achievement at the University of Jordan, finding that female undergraduates earned better grading points average (GPA) than male students. Globally, girls are twice as likely to never start school and are less likely to complete primary and secondary education.

Furthermore, gender-based differences in learning exist with girls performing better on reading tests but worse on science and math tests. Interventions to increase school enrollment and attendance help disadvantaged genders. Studies show that gendered social norms can hinder the benefits of gender-neutral programs for girls in low- and middle-income countries. However, some programs, like female role models and group learning, can provide more benefits for girls. Further research is needed to understand the varying effects of these programs. Policymakers should consider gender-specific constraints in learning interventions, especially when gender gaps exist. Studies often do not consistently report gender differences in program impacts, suggesting that interventions may have gender-neutral effects or not be detectable.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Gender and Development (GAD) remains a critical framework for addressing gender disparities in social, economic, and political spheres. Despite significant global advancements through policies and advocacy efforts, gender inequality continues to be a major challenge, particularly in areas such as labor market participation, wage gaps, political representation, and education. This study has underscored the persistent barriers to gender equality, including institutional biases, deeply ingrained stereotypes, and cultural norms that delay the enforcement of gender-responsive policies.

The disproportionate burden of unpaid domestic labor on women, gendered economic inequalities, and the challenges faced by marginalized groups, including women in rural communities and the LGBTQ+ population. While legal frameworks such as the Magna Carta of Women and gender-responsive initiatives have contributed to progress, their inconsistent implementation remains a key issue. The study also emphasized the need for gender-responsive education to dismantle biases within academic institutions and foster inclusivity in learning environments.

Gender audits and mainstreaming efforts have proven to be essential tools in assessing the effectiveness of gender policies and ensuring accountability in promoting gender equality. However, achieving gender parity requires a multi-faceted approach, including stricter policy enforcement, comprehensive educational reforms, and continuous advocacy for gender-inclusive policies.

Future research should focus on intersectional gender disparities, the inclusion of LGBTQ+ experiences in gender policies, and the evolving impact of digital economies on gender relations by using different research method and approach. Prioritizing gender equality, societies can move toward sustainable development where all individuals, regardless of gender, have equal opportunities to thrive. Only through a holistic and sustained commitment to gender inclusivity can true social, economic, and political equality be achieved.

References

- Abad, M. (2023). Philippines improves in 2023 world gender equality ranking. Philippine Institute for Development Studies. <https://www.pids.gov.ph/details/news/in-the-news/philippines-improves-in-2023-world-gender-equality-ranking>
- Abraha, M., Dagne, A., & Seifu, A. (2019). Gender Responsive Pedagogy: Practices, Challenges & Opportunities - A Case of Secondary Schools of North Wollo Zone, Ethiopia. *Journal of Education Society and Behavioural Science*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jesbs/2019/v30i330128>
- Abulencia, A., Hibanada, R., Bedural, Z., Dellomos, C., & Aggarao, M. (2023). A Qualitative Cross-Sectional Study on Gender Issues in the Schools Division of Marikina: Basis for GAD Policy recommendations. *The Normal Lights*, 17(1). <https://doi.org/10.56278/tnl.v17i1.1890>

- Aikman, S., Unterhalter, E., & Challender, C. (2005). The education MDGs: Achieving gender equality through curriculum and pedagogy change. *Gender & Development*, 13(1), 44–55. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13552070512331332276>
- Akina Mama wa Afrika. (2020). Gender audit tool: A guide for identifying gaps in gender-responsive programming and organizational capacity. Retrieved from [Gender-Audit-Tool FINAL .pdf](#)
- Ananga, E. D. (2021). Gender Responsive Pedagogy for teaching and learning: the practice in Ghana's initial teacher education programme. *Creative Education*, 12(04), 848–864. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2021.124061>
- Ara, E. (2016). Internalizing and externalizing problems in adolescents: Analyzing the gender difference. *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 6(1), 328-337. <https://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:ijrss&volume=6&issue=1&article=020&type=pdf>
- Armar, S. (2024). Gender Equality: An Analysis of Three Organizations in the Philippines. <https://www.theseus.fi/handle/10024/873736>
- Battad, E. (2006). Gender Equality Legislation: Addressing Gender Issues in Conditions of Work (A Policy Review). <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=9ba4de2ebf28d6d1c5a90727ff4c99fe4083ef0d>
- Bejeno, C. (2021). On the frontlines: Peasant women and land reform struggles in the Philippines. https://pure.eur.nl/ws/portalfiles/portal/43218600/final_digital_copy_thesis_cynthia_bejeno.pdf
- Bowles, S., & Gintis, H. (2009). *Schooling in capitalist America: Educational reform and the contradictions of economic life*. Haymarket Books. <https://bit.ly/2RcEDQn>
- Dealca, R. L. (2025). Closing the gap: Advancing gender equality in property rights in the Philippines. Friedrich Naumann Foundation for Freedom. <https://www.freiheit.org/philippines/closing-gap-advancing-gender-equality-property-rights-philippines>
- Deary, I. J., Strand, S., Smith, P., & Fernandes, C. (2006). Intelligence and educational achievement. *Intelligence*, 35(1), 13–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intell.2006.02.001>
- Del Giudice, M. (2015). Differences of genders in the context of personality and social behavior. *ScienceDirect*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com>
- Dizon, A., & Medina, K. (2020). Rapid Gender Analysis Philippines: Metro Manila. 13-17. <https://reliefweb.int/report/philippines/rapid-gender-analysis-philippinesmetro-manila>
- Dorji, T. (2020). Gender Responsive Pedagogy Awareness and Practices. *International Journal of Linguistics and Translation Studies*, 1(2), 100–111. <https://doi.org/10.36892/ijlts.v1i2.21>

- Downey, D. B., & Yuan, A. S. V. (2005). Sex differences in school performance during High School: Puzzling patterns and possible explanations. *Sociological Quarterly*, 46(2), 299–321. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1533-8525.2005.00014.x>
- Dula, T. (2019). Impact of gender inequality in socio-economic development: The case of women in Ethiopia. *Development Country Studies*, 9(11), 46-52.
- Dundić, M. (2024). The social and economic impacts of gender norms. United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). <https://hdr.undp.org/content/2023-gender-social-norms-index-gsni#/indicies/GSNI>
- Eagly, A. H., & Carli, L. L. (2007). Women and the labyrinth of leadership. *Harvard Business Review*, 85(9), 63–71. <https://hbr.org/2007/09/women-and-the-labyrinth-of-leadership>
- Encinas-Franco J., & Laguna, E. (2023). Barriers to Filipino Women’s Political Participation. UP Center for Integrative and Development Studies. <https://cids.up.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Barriers-to-Filipino-Womens-Political-Participation.pdf>
- Gemelli, M.C. (2018, January 29). United Nations Decade for Women. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/United-Nations-Decade-for-Women>
- Grown, C., Addison, T., & Tarp, F. (2016, March 14). Aid for gender equality and development: Lessons and challenges. *Journal of International Development*, 28. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/jid.3211>
- Francis, B. (2002). Boys, girls, and achievement. In Routledge eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203136454>
- Furner, J. (2004). Conceptual analysis: A method for understanding information as evidence, and evidence as information. *Archival science*, 4, 233-265. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10502-005-2594-8>
- Hemillan-Sacro, J., Villegas, J., & Bauyot, M. F. M. (2021). Gender mainstreaming in Barangay governance, City of Mati, Southern Mindanao, Philippines. *Persidangan Antarabangsa Sains Sosial dan Kemanusiaan ke-6 (PASAK6 2021) – Dalam Talian*
- Herrero, C. I. (2019). Gender Analysis Report: The Philippines. 10-12. <https://actionagainsthunger.ph/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/2019-GenderAnalysisPhilippines.pdf>
- Hossain, S., & Chapple, L. (2022). Homophily versus monitoring: Do all female board directors drive the gender assignment of audit partners? *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 41(2). <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0278425422001168>
- International Labour Organization. (2022). The Gender Gap in Employment: What’s Holding Women Back?. *Infostories*. <https://webapps.ilo.org/infostories/en-GB/Stories/Employment/barriers-women#global-gap>

- Jayachandran, S. (2015). The roots of gender inequality in developing countries. *Annual Review of Economics*, 7(1), 63-88. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-economics-080614-115404>
- Jones, R. L. (1993). Library research. In *Journal of AHIMA / American Health Information Management Association* (Vol. 64, Issue 2). Princeton University Press. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-19936-5_3
- Kahamba, J. S., Massawe, F. A., & Kira, E. S. (2017). Awareness and practice of gender-responsive pedagogy in higher learning institutions: the case of Sokoine University of Agriculture, Tanzania.
- Khaiwal, N., & Gupta, S. (2023). Teacher as an Agent for Gender Equality and Gender Sensitivity. *GENDER AND EDUCATION*, 90.
- Khalil, N., Aljanazrah, A., Hamed, G., & Murtagh, E. M. (2023). Teacher educators' perspectives on gender-responsive pedagogy in higher education. *Irish Educational Studies*, 43(4), 903–919. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2023.2174575>
- Lakin, J. M. (2013). Sex differences in reasoning abilities: Surprising evidence that male-female ratios in the tails of the quantitative reasoning distribution have increased. *Intelligence*, 41(4), 263–274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intell.2013.04.004>
- Legewie, J., & DiPrete, T. A. (2009). Family Determinants of the changing gender gap in Educational Attainment: A comparison of the U.S. and Germany. *Journal of Contextual Economics – Schmollers Jahrbuch*, 129(2), 169–180. <https://doi.org/10.3790/schm.129.2.169>
- Libre, J. (2017). “Gender and development in barangay governance, Philippines”. *Journal of Public Administration*, 52 (1): 150–169. <https://journals.co.za/doi/abs/10.10520/EJC-990e9d060>
- Llego, M. A. (2019b, November 21). Updated DePED Gender-Responsive Basic Education Policy. TeacherPH. <https://www.teacherph.com/gender-responsive-policy/>
- Lorber, J. (2008). *The Social Construction of Gender: Paradoxes of Gender*. USA [United States of America]: Yale University. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt1bhkntg>
- Michalko, J. and Maycock, M. (2024) Men in politics as agents of gender equitable change: gender norms and political masculinities. ALIGN report. <https://www.alignplatform.org/sites/default/files/2024-05/meninpolitics-cross-country-report-may24.pdf>
- Mlama, P., Dioum, M., Makoye, H., Murage, L., Wagah, M., & Waskika, R. (2005). *Gender Responsive Pedagogy: A Teacher's Handbook*. Nairobi, Kenya: Forum for African Women.
- Navarro, R. (2015). Gender issues and cyberbullying in children and adolescents: From gender differences to gender identity measures. In *Springer eBooks* (pp. 35–61). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-25552-1_2

- Nekhili, M., Javed, F. & Nagati, H. (2022). Audit Partner Gender, Leadership and Ethics: The Case of Earnings Management. *J Bus Ethics* 177, 233–260. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-021-04757-9>
- Ortiz-Ospina, E., Hasell, J., & Roser, M. (2018). Unequal job opportunities and payment for men and women. *Our World in Data*. <https://ourworldindata.org>
- Parajuli, M., & Thapa, A. (2017). Gender differences in the academic performance of students. *Deleted Journal*, 3(1), 39–47. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jdse.v3i1.27958>
- Paqueo, V. B., & Orbeta, A. C. (2019). Gender equity in education: Helping the boys catch up. PIDS Discussion Paper No. 2019-01 <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/211075/1/166636181X.pdf>
- Philippine Commission on Women. (2009). Republic Act 9710: An Act Providing for the Magna Carta of Women. <https://pcw.gov.ph/magna-carta-of-women>
- Philippine Commission on Women. (2019). Gender Mainstreaming. <https://pcw.gov.ph/gender-mainstreaming/>
- Philippine Commission on Women. (2022). [The Gender and Development Focal Point System Functionality Assessment Tool for National Government Agencies/](#)
- Philippine Institute for Development Studies. (2018). Women sorely underrepresented at top levels of government, industry–study. <https://www.pids.gov.ph/details/women-sorely-underrepresented-at-top-levels-of-government-industry-study>
- Philippine Statistics Authority. (2016). 2016 Gender Statistics on Labor and Employment. <https://psa.gov.ph/content/2016-gender-statistics-labor-and-employment-0>
- Pilongo, L. W. E., & Tirol, G. O. (2013). Mainstreaming Gender Equality and Development in the University of Bohol. *University of Bohol Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 1(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.15631/ubmrj.v1i1.1>
- Quilapio, O. D., Buama, C. a. C., Fuentes, M. D., Gonzales, M. a. S., Callo, E. C., & Dimarucot, M. L. (2024). Gender Inclusivity in Law Enforcement: Impact of Gender-Responsive Policing in Region IV-A, CALABARZON. *Journal of Social Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 3(1), 49–62. <https://doi.org/10.31098/jsetp.v3i1.2519>
- Rarieya, J. F. A., Wango, N. C., Oluga, M., & Abunga, O. (2024). Accelerating Primary Education Tutors' Acquisition of Gender-Responsive Pedagogies. *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*, 5(4), 47–54. <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejedu.2024.5.4.849>
- Reeves, H. (2000). Gender and development: Concepts and definitions. Brighton, 33. <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=959228>
- Reyes, C. M., C. G. Mina, R. D. Asis. (2017). Inequality Of Opportunities Among Ethnic Groups In the Philippines. PIDS Discussion Paper No. 2017-42. <https://pidswebs.pids.gov.ph/CDN/PUBLICATIONS/pidsdps1742.pdf>

- Ridgeway, C. L., & Correll, S. J. (2004). Unpacking the gender system: A theoretical perspective on gender beliefs and social relations. *Gender & Society*, 18(4), 510–531. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0891243204265269>
- Sison, M. (2023). Filipinas stare through the glass ceiling in STEM fields. *Sci Dev Net* <https://www.scidev.net/asia-pacific/features/filipinas-stare-through-the-glass-ceiling-in-stem-fields/>
- Spinath, B., Freudenthaler, H. H., & Neubauer, A. C. (2009). Domain-specific school achievement in boys and girls as predicted by intelligence, personality, and motivation. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 48(4), 481–486. DOI: [10.1016/j.paid.2009.11.028](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2009.11.028)
- Strand, S., Deary, I. J., & Smith, P. (2006). Sex differences in Cognitive Abilities Test scores: A UK national picture. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 76(3), 463–480. <https://doi.org/10.1348/000709905x50906>
- Tantengco, N. S. (2013). Assessment of gender equity in the secondary social studies curriculum: Basis for a proposed guide in preparing gender fair instructional materials. *ATIKAN*, 3(1).
- United Nations Development Programme. (2022). Gender inequality index. Human Development Reports. <https://hdr.undp.org/data-center/thematic-composite-indices/gender-inequality-index#/indicies/GII>
- UN Women-Headquarters.(2022). Handbook on gender mainstreaming for gender equality results, Chapter 1. [Handbook-on-gender-mainstreaming-for-gender-equality-results-en.pdf](#)
- Villegas, J. P., Bauyot, M. F. M., Sacro, J. H., & Siarot, L. D. (2023). Gender audit as basis in developing modules for GAD focal persons in Mati, Davao Oriental, Philippines. *Discourse and Communication for Sustainable Education*, 14(1), 48–56. <https://doi.org/10.2478/dcse-2023-0005>
- Weis, L., & Fine, M. (Eds.). (2005). *Beyond Silenced Voices: Class, Race, and Gender in United States Schools*. SUNY Press. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED361416>